

Predicting Preeclampsia in Primigravida Women during the Second Trimester: A Combined Approach using Doppler Ultrasonography and Clinical Tools

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Abstract:

Background: Preeclampsia is a significant cause of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality worldwide, characterized by hypertension and proteinuria after 20 weeks of gestation. Early identification of women at risk for preeclampsia is crucial for improving outcomes, but traditional prediction methods have limited accuracy. Doppler ultrasonography has emerged as a promising tool for predicting preeclampsia by assessing uterine artery blood flow, particularly through the measurement of pulsatility index (PI) and the detection of diastolic notching.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the predictive value of Doppler ultrasonography in combination with clinical tools for the early detection of preeclampsia in primigravida women during the second trimester.

Methods: Doppler ultrasonography was performed to measure the uterine artery PI and assess the presence of diastolic notching. Clinical data, including blood pressure and body mass index (BMI), were also collected. The primary outcome was the development of preeclampsia. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with logistic regression models employed to determine the predictive value of Doppler findings.

Results: Of the 300 participants, 36 (12%) developed preeclampsia. Elevated PI and the presence of diastolic notching were significantly associated with the development of preeclampsia ($p < 0.001$). The area under the curve (AUC) for PI was 0.83, while the AUC for diastolic notching was 0.77. The combination of these Doppler findings provided an AUC of 0.86, indicating good predictive accuracy.

Conclusion: Doppler ultrasonography, particularly the assessment of uterine artery PI and diastolic notching, is a valuable tool for predicting preeclampsia in primigravida women during the second trimester. The integration of Doppler ultrasonography into routine antenatal care can enhance early risk stratification and improve maternal and fetal outcomes.

Recommendations: Further research is recommended to standardize the use of Doppler ultrasonography in diverse populations and to explore its cost-effectiveness in routine antenatal care. Additionally, incorporating Doppler findings with other clinical and biochemical markers may further improve predictive accuracy.

Keywords: Preeclampsia, Doppler ultrasonography, Uterine artery, Pulsatility index, Primigravida women.

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Introduction

Preeclampsia, a hypertensive disorder, is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in both mothers and infants worldwide, affecting 2-8% of pregnancies. It is characterized in women who were previously normotensive by the appearance of proteinuria and hypertension after 20 weeks of pregnancy. Because preeclampsia is associated with serious consequences like eclampsia, HELLP syndrome (haemolysis, elevated liver enzymes, and low platelet count), premature birth, and foetal growth restriction, early detection, and treatment are critical to improving outcomes for both the mother and the foetus [1,2]. Although the exact

pathophysiology of preeclampsia is unknown, aberrant placentation and endothelial dysfunction are commonly thought to have a role. These anomalies allow the placenta to get insufficient blood flow, which in turn triggers the release of anti-angiogenic substances into the mother's bloodstream and adds to the disease's clinical symptoms [3, 4]. Predicting which women will develop preeclampsia remains difficult, especially in the early stages of pregnancy, despite advancements in our understanding of the condition.

Doppler ultrasonography has become an important diagnostic technique for uterine artery blood flow assessment, as it represents placental perfusion. An increased risk of preeclampsia has been linked to abnormal Doppler results, such as higher uterine artery pulsatility index (PI) and the presence of diastolic notching [5]. Recent research has demonstrated that the prediction of preeclampsia is greatly improved, particularly in the second trimester, when Doppler ultrasonography is combined with additional clinical and biochemical markers [6,7].

Doppler ultrasonography has garnered increasing attention in recent years as a means of detecting preeclampsia early in the prenatal period. Research has indicated that this method is capable of detecting high-risk pregnancies and facilitating prompt interventions, like the use of low-dose aspirin, which has been found to lower the risk of preeclampsia in high-risk women [8,9]. However, several variables can affect how well Doppler ultrasonography predicts preeclampsia, including the population being investigated and the timing of the scan [10]. This study aimed to evaluate the predictive value of Doppler ultrasonography in combination with clinical tools for the early detection of preeclampsia in primigravida women during the second trimester.

Methodology

Study Design: This study employed a prospective cohort design.

Study Setting: The research was conducted in the Obstetrics and Gynaecology Department of DMCH, a tertiary care hospital, over 12 months from April 2019 to March 2020.

Participants: A total of 300 primigravida women in their second trimester of pregnancy were recruited for the study. These women were attending routine antenatal care at the aforementioned hospital.

Inclusion Criteria

- Primigravida women in their second trimester (13-28 weeks of gestation).
- Singleton pregnancy.
- Women who provided written informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Women with a history of chronic hypertension, diabetes mellitus, or renal disease.
- Women with multiple pregnancies (e.g., twins or triplets).
- Women with known congenital anomalies or chromosomal abnormalities in the fetus.

- Women who did not consent to participate in the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were consecutively enrolled from those attending antenatal care clinics during the study period. To reduce observer bias, the Doppler ultrasonography was performed by a single experienced sonographer who was blinded to the clinical data of the participants.

Data Collection: Data were collected through a combination of clinical assessments, Doppler ultrasonographic examinations, and a review of medical records.

- **Clinical Assessments:** Blood pressure, BMI, and other relevant clinical parameters were measured and recorded.
- **Doppler Ultrasonography:** The uterine artery Doppler was performed during the second trimester to assess the PI and presence of diastolic notching. The sonographer was blinded to the participant's clinical information to ensure unbiased measurement.
- **Medical Records:** Relevant clinical data, including baseline characteristics and obstetric history, were extracted from medical records.

Procedure: All participants underwent Doppler ultrasonography between 18-24 weeks of gestation to evaluate uterine artery flow. The PI and the presence or absence of diastolic notching were recorded. Clinical assessments were performed at the same visit to collect data on blood pressure, BMI, and other relevant clinical variables. These data were then analyzed to predict the development of preeclampsia in the third trimester.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was employed for data analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to generate the subjects' baseline characteristics. While continuous variables were presented as mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD), categorical variables were displayed as frequencies and percentages. The initial step was to identify preeclampsia predictors using univariate analysis. Variables that were significant in the univariate analysis were incorporated into a multivariate logistic regression model to account for potential confounders. The odds ratio (OR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated to evaluate the strength of the connections. When the p-value was less than 0.05, statistical significance was reached. A review of the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve was conducted to evaluate the diagnostic predictiveness of clinical tools and Doppler ultrasonography.

Results

A total of 300 primigravida women were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was

26.3 ± 4.2 years, and the mean gestational age at the time of Doppler ultrasonography was 20.5 ± 2.1 weeks. The baseline characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of the Study Participants (N=300)

Characteristic	Mean ± SD / n (%)
Age (years)	26.3 ± 4.2
Gestational age at scan (weeks)	20.5 ± 2.1
Body Mass Index (BMI, kg/m ²)	23.4 ± 3.5
Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	112.6 ± 10.4
Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	72.3 ± 8.7
Uterine artery pulsatility index	1.3 ± 0.4
Uterine artery notching	48 (16%)

Incidence of Preeclampsia: Out of 300 participants, 36 (12%) developed preeclampsia during the third trimester. The mean gestational age at diagnosis of preeclampsia was 33.1 ± 2.6 weeks. The incidence of preeclampsia was significantly

higher in women with abnormal Doppler ultrasonographic findings (elevated pulsatility index and/or presence of diastolic notching) compared to those with normal Doppler results ($p < 0.001$).

Table 2: Incidence of Preeclampsia in Relation to Doppler Ultrasonographic Findings

Doppler Ultrasonography Finding	Preeclampsia (n=36)	No Preeclampsia (n=264)	p-value
Elevated Pulsatility Index	26 (72.2%)	40 (15.2%)	<0.001
Presence of Notching	18 (50.0%)	30 (11.4%)	<0.001
Normal Doppler Findings	6 (16.7%)	194 (73.5%)	<0.001

Predictive Value of Doppler Ultrasonography:

The predictive accuracy of Doppler ultrasonography for preeclampsia was assessed using Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis. The area under the curve (AUC) for the pulsatility index was 0.83 (95% CI: 0.78-0.88),

indicating good predictive value. For the presence of diastolic notching, the AUC was 0.77 (95% CI: 0.71-0.83). The combination of both Doppler findings improved the predictive value, with an AUC of 0.86 (95% CI: 0.82-0.90).

Table 3: ROC Curve Analysis for Predicting Preeclampsia

Predictor	AUC	95% CI	Sensitivity	Specificity
Pulsatility Index	0.83	0.78 - 0.88	72.2%	84.8%
Diastolic Notching	0.77	0.71 - 0.83	50.0%	88.6%
Combined Doppler Findings	0.86	0.82 - 0.90	80.6%	79.5%

Multivariate Analysis: A multivariate logistic regression analysis was conducted to identify independent predictors of preeclampsia. After adjusting for potential confounders such as maternal age, BMI, and baseline blood pressure,

both elevated pulsatility index (OR: 5.24, 95% CI: 2.88-9.52, $p < 0.001$) and presence of diastolic notching (OR: 3.91, 95% CI: 2.08-7.34, $p < 0.001$) remained significant predictors of preeclampsia.

Table 4: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis of Predictors for Preeclampsia

Variable	Adjusted OR	95% CI	p-value
Elevated Pulsatility Index	5.24	2.88 - 9.52	<0.001
Presence of Diastolic Notching	3.91	2.08 - 7.34	<0.001
Maternal Age	1.06	0.98 - 1.15	0.140
Body Mass Index (BMI)	1.15	1.05 - 1.25	0.002
Baseline Systolic Blood Pressure	1.02	1.00 - 1.04	0.045

Discussion

The results of this study indicate that Doppler ultrasonographic findings in the second trimester, particularly elevated uterine artery (PI) and the presence of diastolic notching, are strong predictors

of preeclampsia in primigravida women. Among the 300 participants, 12% developed preeclampsia, with a significantly higher incidence observed in those with abnormal Doppler findings. Specifically, 72.2% of women who developed preeclampsia had

an elevated PI, and 50% had diastolic notching. In contrast, the majority of women with normal Doppler results did not develop preeclampsia, highlighting the predictive value of these ultrasonographic parameters. The statistical analysis further supports the utility of Doppler ultrasonography in predicting preeclampsia. The (AUC) for PI was 0.83, and for diastolic notching, it was 0.77, indicating good predictive accuracy. When both Doppler findings were combined, the AUC increased to 0.86, suggesting that the combination of these two measures provides a more robust prediction model for preeclampsia. This combined approach demonstrated a sensitivity of 80.6% and a specificity of 79.5%, making it a reliable tool for early risk assessment.

Multivariate logistic regression analysis revealed that elevated PI and the presence of diastolic notching were independently associated with an increased risk of preeclampsia, even after adjusting for other potential confounders such as maternal age, BMI, and baseline blood pressure. The adjusted odds ratios for PI and notching were 5.24 and 3.91, respectively, emphasizing the significant role of these Doppler findings in predicting preeclampsia. In summary, the study underscores the importance of Doppler ultrasonography as a predictive tool for preeclampsia in primigravida women. The findings suggest that incorporating Doppler ultrasonographic assessments into routine antenatal care could enhance early detection and allow for timely interventions to mitigate the risks associated with preeclampsia, ultimately improving maternal and fetal health outcomes.

In a prospective diagnostic investigation conducted at an Armed Forces tertiary care facility, assessed the prognostic efficacy of uterine artery Doppler in the second trimester of pregnancy. The research discovered that preeclampsia may be accurately predicted by the resistivity index (RI) and pulsatility index (PI). In particular, RI values of ≥ 0.7 had a sensitivity of 44.78% and specificity of 89.72%, whereas uterine artery PI values of ≥ 1.3 had a sensitivity of 79.1% and specificity of 70.8%. According to a study, uterine artery Doppler imaging is a good method for estimating the chance of preeclampsia during the second trimester [11]. The use of uterine artery Doppler during the first trimester to predict preeclampsia at the People's College of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, Bhopal was investigated. With a 96.7% specificity, the study discovered a substantial correlation between the onset of preeclampsia and a pulsatility index greater than 1.71. The study concluded that uterine artery Doppler is a useful method for anticipating preeclampsia in the early stages of pregnancy, especially when examining the uterine artery's diastolic notch and PI simultaneously [12].

To increase prediction accuracy, the study stressed the combined use of placental vascular indicators and uterine artery Doppler imaging. The placental volume and uterine artery Doppler indices (PI and RI) exhibited higher specificity in predicting preeclampsia, whereas the placental vascular indices (VI, FI, and VFI) showed higher sensitivity. According to the study, using these resources could help predict preeclampsia early and accurately [13].

Conclusion

Doppler ultrasonography, specifically the assessment of uterine artery pulsatility index and diastolic notching, is an effective method for predicting preeclampsia in primigravida women during the second trimester. The use of this non-invasive tool, in combination with clinical assessments, can enhance the early identification of women at risk for developing preeclampsia, thereby improving maternal and fetal outcomes.

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